

A CREATIVE APPROACH TO TRAINING FUTURE PEDAGOGUES- JOURNALISTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Each field has its own terminology. These terms are becoming more popular over the years. If a new word appears in one country today, it is a natural phenomenon that it will spread to other countries as well. The reason for the popularization of this process is the expansion of the tasks of a certain field, where the term appeared, and the increase of its importance in society. Today, the field of journalism is one of the rapidly developing fields.

Keywords: *Journalism, education, pedagogical activities, scientific-theoretical, philosophical-aesthetic foundations.*

The training of future pedagogues-journalists in higher education involves the quality training of highly qualified journalist personnel at the level of national and international standards, who have deeply mastered the field of journalism, its specific features, scientific-theoretical, philosophical-aesthetic foundations, modern media technologies [Irnazarov K.T., Mamatova Ya.M., 2002].

Taking into account the achievements of our country in the field of mass communication and journalism, the experience of educational institutions of foreign countries, and the demands and needs of mass media operating in the regions, creation of educational and methodological literature in relevant areas and specialties, as well as introducing modern information technologies and distance learning methods into the educational process, solving the scientific and methodological tasks of the development of journalism education, carrying out scientific research aimed at introducing advanced foreign technologies, and encouraging talented students and young people to engage in scientific activities broad involvement in dealing with [Voroshilov V.V. Journalism, 1999].

To implement educational and scientific projects, to widely involve specialists in the process of education and scientific research, to develop cooperation relations with the leading republican and foreign higher educational institutions and scientific

centers in the field of pedagogy, to attract promising young graduates to foreign higher educational institutions and to increase the scientific and pedagogical potential of the University by regularly sending them to study at the master's and doctoral degrees of the scientific centers, to retrain and improve the qualifications of mass media specialists of the republic, to form a scientific-methodical base and to implement educational-methodical leadership pedagogue - develops the love and interest of journalists in their field. In the educational process of training future pedagogues-journalists in higher education institutions, several creative approaches and practical exercises in organizational-management and production and service activities, information-analytical activities for future pedagogic journalists in higher education institutions Bachelor's degree allows journalists to improve their knowledge and experience.

In organizational - management and production and service activities

- Establishment of mass media activities, establishment of its legal bases, organizational structures and activities carried out on the basis of the law; development and implementation of quality management processes of production activities;

- planning the creative team of employees, tools and resources necessary for the implementation of production processes;

- development of methods and mechanisms for monitoring and quality assessment of production processes related to the creation and use of information technology systems;

- development of mechanisms for monitoring and quality assessment of production processes using information technologies;

- control of production processes in terms of compliance with environmental protection and labor safety requirements;

- organization and management of social and spiritual-educational work in the team;

- making the right and healthy decision in the conditions of different opinions,

- drawing up a work plan for the activities being performed, monitoring and evaluating the results of the work performed [Khudaikulov M., 2011: 288].

In information - analytical activity

- developing and using journalistic creative skills and abilities in scientific and practical activities;

- compliance with the national and international code of professional ethics;

- planning of resources necessary for the implementation of production processes;
- development and implementation of management processes that ensure the quality of production activities;
- ensuring environmental protection, fire, equipment and labor safety in production processes;
- examination of projects, resources, literature, electronic video and audio products on relevant topics;
- rendering of consulting services in fields suitable for specialization;
- to be able to provide appropriate service in the field, to be able to use consulting, translation, information gathering methods and organizational work in the field of journalism;

In conclusion, practical training is held separately for each academic group in an auditorium equipped with multimedia devices. Classes are conducted using active and interactive methods, use of "Case-study" technology. Transmission of visual materials and information using multimedia devices. Also, based on the topic, conducting the lesson in the form of a mobile lesson at the Museum of Literature and Art will contribute to the development of higher education journalism students [Lazutina L., 2000].

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